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SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITION OF THE FRUIT AND VEGETABLE NETWORK OF UZBEKISTAN AT THE BEGINNING OF INDEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with analysis of the socio-economic condition of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the end of the 80s of the 20th century scientifically and historically, and instance of revealing the cotton monopoly implemented during the former union and its impact on the life of our country According to the results of the research of the scientific article, conclusions and suggestions were given based on a historical approach to the abolition of the cotton monopoly on the eve of independence and the role and prospects of the fruit and vegetable sector of agriculture in the life of our country.

Key words: *Southern regions, fruits and vegetables, cotton monopoly, collective farm, state farm, processing industry.*

For as long as humanity has existed, it has always felt the need for quality food products. Acceleration of the processes of globalization and urbanization in the regions of the world, together with socio-economic development, the rapid growth of the population and the ever-increasing need for agricultural products have significantly increased. It also requires intensive development of the economic system. This leads to an increase in interest in studying the development trends in the creation of human life support in different cultural and economic areas of the world in the context of different historical periods.

The Millennium Development Program of the United Nations also includes a priority direction, which envisages the intensive development of agriculture and the production of natural and ecologically clean products. World experience shows that factors such as the growing share of fruits, vegetables and dairy products in the diet are the reasons for the future development of fruit and vegetable products. Analysis of the state of the world fruit and vegetable sector shows that today China, the USA and the European Union account for the share of the world community in the production and export of fruit and vegetable products [1, 85-89].

In the first years of independence, special attention was paid to the development and progress of the agricultural sector, which is considered an important sector in the economy of our country. Because during the period of Soviet power, agriculture fell into a difficult situation, and the livelihood of agrarian specialists decreased. Instead of remunerating the work of specialists and providing material and moral incentives, “socialist competitions” were organized, and appreciation of “specially” selected “labor winners” - brigadiers, mechanics, engineers - was put on the agenda.

As a result, by the end of the 1980s, Uzbekistan, like the entire Union, faced a deep social and economic crisis. The situation in Uzbekistan was very difficult compared to other republics within the Union [2, 13].

If we look at the history, we can see in the numbers that during the time of the former union, our country was specialized in the agricultural sector, and the cotton monopoly that dominated the republic’s economy for many years did not allow the development of other industries. The fruit and vegetable sector of the researched agriculture has a much lower interest rate compared to other sectors in our country particular, according to the information stored in the National Archives of Uzbekistan, let’s talk about the activity of the fruit and vegetable industry in our country before independence. “Uz meva sabzavot uzum sanoat” republican agro-industry association was established in 1975 to develop agro-industry cooperation in Uzbekistan. This association was engaged in the cultivation and processing of fruits, grapes, vegetables, potatoes. Historically, more than 300 types of fruits and vegetables have been grown

in the countries of the world and new local selection varieties have been created. Later, on the basis of this association, the Ministry of Fruit and Vegetable Farms of the Republic was established in 1981. This ministry united 275 specialized state farms, 18 wineries and 11 canneries, where more than 190 thousand people worked. The republican agro-industrial association included scientific production departments. By the mid-1980s, there were 15 production agrarian associations, which included 79 horticultural and viticultural farms, including 10 state farms, as well as 7 wineries and 6 canneries. [3, 85-86]. Information on the activities of farms specializing in fruit and vegetable growing in Altinsoy, Sariosiyo, Denov Termiz, Uzun, Zhargorgon districts of the southern Surkhandarya region of Uzbekistan was calculated within the indicated figures [4, 139].

The number of inter-farm enterprises and organizations that need to integrate agro-industry has increased significantly. They served as the main factor in the improvement of the republic's economy and the transfer of agriculture to an industrial basis. Along with the public sector, individual farms also played an important role in increasing agricultural production.

The leadership of Uzbekistan tried to implement this task by firmly linking the solution to the problem of employment of the rural population. Population employment is considered the most important factor of the social sphere. People who were not employed in public production worked on their farms and in the beginning of the 80s of the 20th century, they grew fruit and vegetable products in the amount of 2.5 billion soums, which is almost a quarter of all agricultural products produced in Uzbekistan. However, the failure of its maintenance and processing enterprises to meet the demand has caused considerable wastage. It is found in archival data that processed and prepared fruit and vegetable products are of low quality, and in some cases, they are diagnosed as unusable [5, 18].

On the eve of independence, the first effort to alleviate the acute agrarian problems in Uzbekistan, especially the socio-economic situation in the republic's villages, began only after the top leadership of the republic was replaced. In 1989, the first President

of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov, was appointed to the new leadership of the republic. It is worth noting that the new leadership openly announced that it had waged a fierce struggle against the cotton monopoly during the lifetime of that autocratic regime. As a result of the measures taken by the leadership of the republic (reduction of the areas planted with seeds, moderation of the cotton production plan, etc.), the weight of cotton in the total amount of cultivated areas was reduced to 63.9% as early as 1989. After Uzbekistan gained independence, a period of development in the agricultural sector began. For the Uzbek farmer, who has been used to being a “collective farmer” for 70 years, the “new way” of creating farms became a motivation for him to move towards the future. That’s why this news became widespread in a short period of time. On April 1, 1991, there were 6,143 farms in the republic, of which 4,666 specialized in milk production, and 1,477 specialized in cattle breeding [6, 18].

Figure 1. The composition of cultivated areas in Uzbekistan on the eve of independence (in %) [7]

If we pay attention to the diagram in Fig. 1, in 1990, on the eve of independence in Uzbekistan, there were drastic changes in agriculture, and the territorial distribution of total cultivated areas was revised. The fight against the cotton monopoly began. But

the figures for this period also indicated that the cotton monopoly was dominant. The scientifically based system of crop rotation has been broken, the land has lost its fertility, and the shortage of water resources has increased. Serious difficulties have arisen in providing the population with food products. Explaining this situation, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov said: “First of all, it is necessary to tell us that the fragile, weak, unilaterally developed cotton monopoly and the economy built on the basis of uncontrolled and merciless use of rich mineral raw material resources have left a heavy legacy. Another feature of this heavy legacy is the republic’s dependence on the center in the matter of fuel and grain, which is evident in the importation of the most important foodstuffs such as flour, sugar, sugar, dairy products, other consumer goods, and ready-made products from abroad. Appears” [8, 270].

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 31, 1991, large-scale reforms were implemented in all areas. In particular, it was implemented in agriculture. This economy, which is one of the important sectors of the economy, contributed almost 17.5% of the country’s gross domestic product, about 30% of the employed people, and also 64% of the population lived in rural areas [9 , 3]. When we talk about agriculture, first of all, in the market economy of our country, while meeting the demand of the population for food products and industry for raw materials, increasing the export potential is one of the most important tasks facing agriculture today. remains. The government of our republic pays great attention to this area. Fruit and vegetable growing, which is one of the important branches of agriculture, is a human food product and is an integral part of human life.

There is a daily demand for food products, which are part of the basic human needs. It is known that during the period of the former regime in Uzbekistan there was production of agricultural products, but their processing industries and enterprises lagged behind in development and were not modernized. Farmers handed over the products grown in all branches of agriculture to state farms and collective farms.

According to the information provided by the State Statistics Organization of Uzbekistan in 1990, it was calculated as follows.

Including:

The number of collective farms is 940;

The number of state farms is 1108.

This system limited the independent activity of the peasant. In order to solve this problem, our government started supporting farming activities in the republic's agriculture in the late 1990s. Dekhkon (farming) farms, which had the right to operate independently, began to be established in it, mainly operating collective farms and state farms. They grew agricultural products and handed them over to collective farms and state farms. Since 1991, dekhon (farm) holdings with the status of independent legal entities have been established. Since 1998, farms have been established and developed in accordance with this law.

Research on the topic of the article and their results show that during the former union, Uzbekistan was used as a raw material base for cotton only on the basis of biased bias. According to the statistical data of 1990, Uzbekistan has a population of more than 19 million people, and the fact that 70% of the population is engaged in agriculture is a very sad situation. Because the industry of the 21st century is very low compared to developed countries.

Our developed life today confirms that with the achievement of independence, all areas were developed equally, we entered the world community based on capitalist market relations and took steps towards integration.

Based on the analysis, discussion and results, the suggestions are as follows:

1. At a time when the processes of globalization and urbanization are developing, in order to restore greenness and ecological balance, it is necessary to pay great attention to the development of the fruit and vegetable industry and increase its territory.

2. Based on the priorities set at the meeting of video selectors held on November 2, 2021 under the chairmanship of The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, it is considered appropriate to bring the framework of the national project “Green Space” [10] to the world level in our country.

3. In order to develop the fruit and vegetable industry in Uzbekistan, it is appropriate to establish a specialized channel by the Uzbek TV and Radio company.

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